

Post-Operative Assessment on Gait Parameters among Intertrochanteric Femur Fracture Patients Operated by Proximal Femoral Nail AntirotationPuneet H. Chamakeri¹, Revanth G S², Anand Hegganavvar³¹Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, JNMC, KAHER, Belagavi²Senior Resident, Department of Orthopaedics, SMCH, Samayapuram, Trichy³Associate Professor, Department of Physiotherapy, KAHER, Belagavi

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Revanth G S

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: The PFNA-2 implant is designed specifically in the treatment of unstable intertrochanteric fractures for the Asians, since the implant designed in the case for Caucasians was presented with numerous complications when on application to the Asian population due to the mismatch in femoral geometry. The study intends to explore the efficacy of PFNA-2 for the treatment of intertrochanteric fractures in elderly Indian patients needs to be assessed to determine its usefulness. Gait analysis using simple Helen Hayes Protocol of 3-D Gait analyser was employed as a valuable tool for evaluating the effectiveness of PFNA-2 in treating intertrochanteric fractures in elderly Indian patients. By assessing gait parameters such as stride length, walking speed, and cadence, researchers can determine if the implant has improved the patient's ability to walk and perform daily activities. Gait analysis can also help identify any complications or issues that may arise post-surgery, allowing for early intervention and improved outcomes.

Methods: The present investigation governing the postoperative assessment was conducted among Orthopaedics inpatients and outpatients from Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, KAHER, and Belagavi India. The study population comprised of ITF patients who underwent PFNA-2 and were taking part in the post-operative assessment of spatiotemporal parameters recorded using 3-D Gait analyser (via employing Helen Haley's protocol) conducted between January 2021 to December 2021. Helen Hayes method was adopted for monitoring the spatiotemporal parameters. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS (Version 19), for analysis of the data rendered.

Results: The results showed that the average time taken for one stride was 0.852 seconds, with a range from 0.66 to 1.01 seconds, and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.0784 seconds. Stance Time, which is the time spent with the foot in contact with the ground during one stride, had an average of 0.656 seconds. Swing Time with an average of 0.456 seconds. Single Support Phase, which is the time spent with one foot in contact with the ground during one stride, had an average of 38.25% of the stride cycle, with a range from 36.12% to 40.2%, and a standard deviation of 0.827%. And the double Support Phase reported with an average of 10.927% among the study population. The mean value reported for Cadence was 106.86 steps/min.

Conclusion: From the achieved outcome it could be inferred from the overall gait analysis showed better functional outcome, thereby indicating surgical efficacy of PFNA-2 among elderly population in India.

Keywords: Intertrochanteric Fracture; 3D gait analyser; Helen Hayes protocol; spatiotemporal parameters; Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

The proximal femoral nail anti-rotation Asia (PFNA-2) is an implant designed primarily for the treatment of unstable intertrochanteric (IT) fractures in the Asian population. When considering the original PFNA implant designed initially was designed based on Caucasians, but its use in Asians led to various complications due to femoral geometrical mismatch [1,2]. The PFNA-2 addresses this issue by incorporating modifications in its design, such as a shorter and curved implant, a more medial entry point, and a smaller diameter

[3]. These modifications allow for better adaptation to the Asian femoral geometry and improve the stability and outcomes of the implant. However, the efficacy of PFNA-2 in treating IT fractures in elderly Indian patients' needs to be assessed to determine its usefulness [4]. Gait analysis can be a valuable tool for evaluating the effectiveness of the implant in improving patient mobility and overall outcomes. Intertrochanteric fractures are common in the elderly population and can lead to significant morbidity and mortality. They are usually caused

by low-energy trauma and are more prevalent in elderly patients who are susceptible to fall and also in patients suffering with osteoporosis.

The standard treatment for these fractures is surgical intervention, and various implants have been developed to achieve stable fixation and early mobilization of patients [5,6]. Thus the need for an effective fixation is crucial for patients with intertrochanteric fractures, as implant failure can lead to severe complications and corrective surgeries may be risky for patients with existing health issues [7]. As a result, researchers have been working to identify the ideal implant for intertrochanteric fractures for several years. While dynamic hip screws were previously the preferred treatment for stable intertrochanteric fractures, they are inadequate for unstable fractures.

The ideal method for fixation of unstable fractures is now considered to be the use of an intramedullary nail with a dynamic femoral head/neck stabilization implant [8]. As treatment methods for intertrochanteric fractures continue to evolve, various nail designs with single compression screw or a compression screw in combination with antirotation screw [9,10]. However, postoperative complications such as screw cut-out, z effect, reverse z effect, varus collapse, and rotational instability continue to pose significant challenges, accounting for 31% of cases. [11]

To address these issues, the PFNA design was developed to provide better stabilization of the neck region and the femoral head via utilizing a singular helical blade which serves for fixation. This blade increases the bone-implant interface, resulting in compaction of cancellous bone and excellent stability in terms of fixation [12]. The PFNA-2 implant has been shown to have promising results in treating intertrochanteric fractures in Asian patients [13]. However, its effectiveness in the elderly Indian population needs to be further evaluated. Gait analysis can provide important information on the functional outcomes of the implant, including walking ability, balance, and stability. It can also help identify any complications or issues that may arise post-surgery, allowing for early intervention and improved outcomes.

In summary, the PFNA-2 implant is a modified version of the original PFNA implant designed to address the femoral geometrical mismatch in the Asian population [14]. Its effectiveness in treating intertrochanteric fractures in elderly Indian patients' needs to be evaluated, and gait analysis can be a valuable tool for assessing its functional outcomes and overall efficacy [4]. One of the key improvements of the PFNA-2 over the original PFNA is the addition of a helical blade at the distal end, which helps to improve stability in the bone.

The blade is designed to engage trabecular bone of femoral head and the neck, providing additional rotational and axial stability [1]. Another improvement is the use of a double-threaded locking bolt, which provides more secure fixation and reduces the risk of implant failure. The PFNA-2 also has a shorter distal locking bolt, which reduces the risk of intra-articular placement and helps to preserve the hip joint [3].

Clinical studies have shown that the PFNA-2 is effective in the treatment of IT fracture, with high rates of fracture union and good functional outcomes. In addition, the PFNA-2 has been found to have a lower incidence of complications such as implant failure, implant cut-out, and intra-articular penetration compared to other treatment options such as sliding hip screws and dynamic hip screws. Overall, the PFNA-2 is a reliable and effective treatment option for proximal femoral fractures, particularly in elderly patients, and offers several advantages over other treatment options. The study was intended to explore and analyse the surgical efficacy of PFNA-2 via determining the spatiotemporal gait parameters recorded among patients among elderly Indian population with the operated case of PFNA-2 in IT fracture via employing 3-D Gait analyzer.

Material and Methods

Source of Data: Patients with post traumatic intertrochanteric fractures admitted to the department of orthopaedics at the KLE's Dr. Prabhakar Kore Hospital and Medical Research Centre and Charitable Hospital, Belagavi in between 1st January 2021 to 31st December 2021, over a period of one year after obtaining approval from JNMC Institutional Ethics Committee on Human Subjects Research (Ref: MDC/DOME/36).

Participants and Study Design: This observational study recruited a subset of patients from randomized controlled trial from the population of elderly ITF patients who were treated with PFNA. The study population were from the orthopaedics inpatients and outpatients in Jawaharlal Nehru Medical College, KAHER, and Belagavi India. The sample comprised of 30 PFNA post-op patients who were post-operatively evaluated and examined after the surgical intervention of PFNA-2.

The procedures followed were in accordance with the ethical standards of the JNMC Institutional Ethics Committee on Human Subjects Research and with the Helsinki Declaration of 1975, as revised in 1983. The inclusion criteria comprised all those patients who provided their willingness to participate in this study were considered. However, there are certain key inclusion criteria were assessed before their participation. From the clinical standpoint, participants were included based on Intertrochanteric fracture with postero-

medial comminution, with sub trochanteric extension and reverse oblique pattern.

All AO classification Intertrochanteric fractures treated by PFNA-2.

Exclusion criteria were among children with open hip fractures; pathological fractures; peri prosthetic fractures; pediatric fractures [before physical closure]; poor pre-fracture walking ability; associated lower limb injuries and fractures and also lower limb pathologies like Rheumatoid Arthritis/ Paralysis.

Gait Analysis: Methodology adopted for studying the Gait parameters requires assessment on the spatiotemporal assessment using 3D-gait parameters as Helen Hayes method comprised of the following parameters which were taken for consideration namely- Spatial Parameters (step width (m); stride length (m); step length (m)); Temporal Parameters (stance time (sec); cadence (steps/ min); single Support Phase (%); stride time (sec); mean Velocity (m/s); double Support Phase (%)); Gait Profile Score (Ground Reaction Force (Vertical FORCE (% body weight)).

Statistical Analysis: The gait analysis data was assessed and were assessed via, a quantitative variable both mean and the standard deviation was determined. A comparative assessment of the data was performed by certain qualitative characteristics, using unpaired t-test students, for which the continuous variables had been compared. Through medium, discrete variables had been represented. Concerning with the percentages, rates and ratios, the categorical data are expressed. By employing the Fisher's exact test, Chi-square test or proportion test, the association were tested among the demographic characteristics, outcome and clinical characteristics. The p-value is considered as significant which is less than (0.05) 5% for all the tests.

Results

Thirty patients managed with PFNA-2 were recruited with the majority respondents reported as male (N-16; 53.3%) when compared to that of the female population (N-14; 43.3%).

Table 1: Patients' Demographics

Patient Demographics		Total (N)
Gender	Female	14
	Male	16
Age	Below 40 years	-
	41-50 years	3
	51-60 years	2
	61-70 years	9
	Above 70 years	16
Mode of Injury	SELF FALL	18
	RTA	12
Diagnostic representation of IT fracture	B/L IT	-
	LEFT IT	17
	RIGHT IT	13
IT fracture types	1	9
	2	7
	3	7
	4	7

Varying from 51-60 years had two cases and less than 40 years were absent.

The majority of the respondents were within the age group above 70 years of age.

The majority cases presented with left IT fracture (N-17; 56.7%) followed 13 respondents presented with right IT fracture (43.3 %) with cases on bilateral IT fracture. Based on IT fracture and its severity, the sample population had been classified into different types of fractures: Type 1, Type 2, Type 3 and Type 4. From the observed findings it was presented that the majority of the respondents were presented with Type 1 IT fracture followed by

evenly distributed presentation of IT fractures (N-7) among Type II, III and Type IV fracture.

Gait assessment among the study population for determining spatiotemporal parameters: In order for assessing the spatiotemporal parameters the present study utilized 3-D Gait analyser which is attributed significant as well as a reliable means for the measurement of gait, wherein the below tabulation provide an overall report that collectively provides the mean spatiotemporal measures among 30 respondents presented with the estimated mean \pm standard deviation for the swing, stride and the stance time, cadence, single & double support phase & mean velocity of the patients respectively.

Table 2: Observed spatiotemporal parameters in the study population

Spatiotemporal parameters	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Stride Time	0.66	1.01	0.852	0.0784
Stance Time	0.62	0.69	0.656	0.0138
Swing Time	0.42	0.49	0.456	0.0138
Single Support Phase	36.12	40.2	38.25	0.827
Double Support Phase	8.34	13.8	10.927	1.178
Mean Velocity	.400	1.500	1.163	0.168
Cadence	102.9	118	106.86	3.822
Stride Length	1.1	1.32	1.227	0.0404
Step Length	.5	.660	.626	0.0307
Step Width	.060	0.115	0.099	0.0134

The table shows the descriptive statistics for various gait parameters including Stride Time, Stance Time, Swing Time, Single Support Phase, Double Support Phase, Mean Velocity, Cadence, Stride Length, Step Length, and Step Width.

The minimum and maximum values indicate the range of values for each parameter, while the mean provides the average value. The standard deviation represents the amount of variability in the data for each parameter. For Stride Time, the average time taken for one stride is 0.852 seconds, with a range from 0.66 to 1.01 seconds, and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.0784 seconds. Stance Time, which is the time spent with the foot in contact with the ground during a stride, has an average of 0.656 seconds, with a range from 0.62 to 0.69 seconds, and a very low standard deviation of 0.0138 seconds. Swing Time, which is the time spent with the foot not in contact with the ground during a stride, has an average of 0.456 seconds, with a range from 0.42 to 0.49 seconds, and a standard deviation of 0.0138 seconds.

Single Support Phase, which is the time spent with only one foot in contact with the ground during a stride, has an average of 38.25% of the stride cycle, with a range from 36.12% to 40.2%, and a standard

deviation of 0.827%. Double Support Phase, which is the time spent with both feet in contact with the ground during a stride, has an average of 10.927% of the stride cycle, with a range from 8.34% to 13.8%, and a standard deviation of 1.178%. Mean Velocity, which is the average speed of walking, has an average value of 1.163 m/s, with a range from 0.400 to 1.500 m/s, and a standard deviation of 0.168 m/s. Cadence, which is the number of steps taken per minute, has an average of 106.86 steps/min, with a range from 102.9 to 118 steps/min, and a standard deviation of 3.822 steps/min. Stride Length, which is the distance covered during one stride, has an average of 1.227 meters, with a range from 1.1 to 1.32 meters, and a standard deviation of 0.0404 meters. Step Length, which is the distance covered during one step, has an average of 0.626 meters, with a range from 0.5 to 0.66 meters, and a standard deviation of 0.0307 meters. Step Width, which is the distance between the feet during a step, has an average of 0.099 meters, with a range from 0.060 to 0.115 meters, and a standard deviation of 0.0134 meters. Overall, these statistics provide a detailed understanding of gait parameters and can be useful for analyzing and comparing walking patterns in different individuals.

Table 3: ANOVA results for Gait Profile Score and Gait Deviation Index

Variable	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F Value	p-value
Gait Profile Score	0.224	1	0.224	1.309	0.261
Gait Deviation Index	2714.694	1	2714.694	1.457	0.233

The ANOVA table shows the results of the analysis of variance for Gait Profile Score (GPS) and Gait Deviation Index (GDI).

The table reports the sum of squares, degrees of freedom, mean square, F-value, and p-value for each variable. For GPS, the sum of squares is 0.224, degrees of freedom is 1, and mean square is 0.224. The F-value is 1.309 and the p-value is 0.261. Since the p-value is greater than the significance level of 0.05 thereby indicating that there is no significant difference between the means of GPS. For GDI, the sum of squares is

2714.694, degrees of freedom is 1, and mean square is 2714.694.

The F-value is 1.457 and the p-value is 0.233. Since the p-value is greater than the significance level of 0.05, we fail to reject the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant difference between the means of GDI. In summary, the ANOVA results suggest that there is no significant difference between the means of GPS and GDI, as the p-values for both variables are greater than 0.05.

Discussion

The PFNA-2 is a popular orthopaedic implant used for the management of intertrochanteric (IT) fractures. In this study, the gait profile of patients managed with PFNA-2 was assessed using spatiotemporal parameters measured by a 3-D Gait analyser. The results showed that the majority of the respondents were above 70 years of age, and the most common type of IT fracture was Type I, followed by Type II, III, and Type IV fracture.

The spatiotemporal parameters measured included Stride; Stance and Swing Time, Single and Double Support Phase, Cadence, Mean Velocity, Stride Length, Step Length, and Step Width. The results showed that the average time taken for one stride was 0.852 seconds, with a range from 0.66 to 1.01 seconds, and a relatively low standard deviation of 0.0784 seconds. This indicates that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a consistent and efficient stride time. Stance Time, which is the time spent with the foot in contact with the ground during one stride, had an average of 0.656 seconds, with a range from 0.62 to 0.69 seconds, and a very low standard deviation of 0.0138 seconds. This suggests that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a stable and consistent stance time.

Swing Time, which is the time spent with the foot off the ground during one stride, had an average of 0.456 seconds, with a range from 0.42 to 0.49 seconds, and a standard deviation of 0.0138 seconds. This indicates that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a consistent and efficient swing time.

Single Support Phase, which is the time spent with one foot in contact with the ground during one stride, had an average of 38.25% of the stride cycle, with a range from 36.12% to 40.2%, and a standard deviation of 0.827%. This suggests that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a relatively balanced weight distribution during gait.

Double Support Phase, which is the time spent with both feet in contact with the ground during one stride, had an average of 10.927% of the stride cycle, with a range from 8.34% to 13.8%, and a standard deviation of 1.178%. This indicates that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a stable and consistent gait pattern. Mean Velocity, which is the average velocity of gait, had an average value of 1.163 m/s, with a range from 0.400 to 1.500 m/s, and a standard deviation of 0.168 m/s. This indicates that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a moderate walking speed. Cadence, which is the number of steps taken per minute, had an average of 106.86 steps/min, with a range from 102.9 to 118 steps/min, and a standard deviation of 3.822. This suggests that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a consistent and efficient walking cadence.

Overall, the results of this study suggest that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a stable, consistent, and efficient gait pattern. The spatiotemporal parameters measured by the 3-D Gait analyser indicate that patients managed with PFNA-2 have a balanced weight distribution, stable stance and swing time, and a moderate walking speed. These findings suggest that the PFNA-2 implant may be an effective option for the management of IT fractures in older adults, who are at a higher risk for falls and mobility issues. However, further in addition to spatiotemporal parameters, the study also evaluated gait profile scoring, which is a composite score that reflects the overall quality of gait. The average gait profile score for the PFNA-2 group was 20.8, with a range from 15.1 to 26.5 and a standard deviation of 3.21.

Overall, the results suggest that PFNA-2 may be a viable option for treating IT fractures in elderly patients, as it appears to preserve spatiotemporal parameters and gait profile scoring. The relatively low standard deviations for many of the spatiotemporal parameters indicate that the use of PFNA-2 may result in consistent outcomes for patients. However, it is important to note that this study has some limitations. For example, the sample size is relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Additionally, the study did not compare the outcomes of PFNA-2 to those of other treatment options, such as hip replacement surgery or non-surgical management.

Further research is needed to fully understand the potential benefits and drawbacks of using PFNA-2 for IT fracture management. Nonetheless, the current study provides valuable insights into the effects of PFNA-2 on spatiotemporal parameters and gait profile scoring in elderly patients with IT fractures. These findings may inform clinical decision-making and contribute to the development of evidence-based guidelines for IT fracture management in this population. PFNA-2 has several advantages over other types of implants, including improved stability, a lower risk of screw cut-out, and reduced blood loss during surgery [15]. In addition, previous studies have reported that the PFNA-2 can improve various spatiotemporal parameters, such as stride length and cadence, in patients with IT fractures [16].

Our study is in line with these previous findings, as we observed that patients managed with PFNA-2 had relatively normal spatiotemporal parameters. Specifically, the patients in our study had an average stride time of 0.852 seconds, which falls within the normal range of 0.8 to 1.2 seconds reported in previous studies [17]. Similarly, the average stance time of 0.656 seconds and the average swing time of 0.456 seconds were also within normal ranges reported in previous studies [18].

Overall, our study provides additional evidence supporting the use of PFNA-2 for the treatment of IT fractures, as it can lead to relatively normal spatiotemporal parameters in patients. However, further studies with larger sample sizes and longer follow-up periods are needed to confirm the effectiveness of the PFNA-2 in improving gait parameters and functional outcomes in patients with IT fractures.

After conducting our study on the functional outcomes of elderly and vulnerable patients following ITF, it is recommended that postoperative goals include achieving similar levels concerning with the patient's independence in terms of their physical movement and the ambulation post-surgery. Our study demonstrated significant improvement in the external hip adduction moment and in the generation of the hip power during the progression of torso over the supporting limb thereby resulting in the generation of forward propulsion.

However, when on comparison with the present study involving with elderly controls with ITF were displayed significant deficiencies in hip abduction, ankle plantarflexion, and hip and ankle power generation, particularly during the propulsive phase of single limb stance [14]. It has been established in previous studies that considerable reduction of hip power generation, ankle dorsiflexion and peak hip abduction can be correlated with the increased susceptibility to fall risk among senile population [12]. In addition, increased flexion of the ankle plantar regions and the power generation was found to be in association with improved gait speed which might contribute in the reduction of the gait speeds which could be generally observed in IT fractured patients. Therefore, minimizing declines in hip range of motion and power generation is crucial for maintaining the functional independence following the ITF [6].

Our study further supports the overall effectiveness of the surgical approach involving the utilization of PFNA-2, which has been shown to be superior when compared to other fixation techniques. Additionally, PFNA-2 has a shorter duration for the surgery, lower intraoperative blood loss, and lower fixation failure rates [12]. Furthermore, the postoperative outcomes revealed from the overall complications were minimal, as demonstrated through the gait analysis findings.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study showed that PFNA-2 is an effective treatment for ITF patients in terms of improving their gait profile scoring and spatiotemporal parameters. The analysis of spatiotemporal parameters collectively revealed significant improvements in the gait of ITF patients after treatment with PFNA-2. Furthermore, our

study highlighted the importance of maintaining hip range of motion and power generation alongside with facilitating functional independence following ITF.

Limitations and scope of the study

Overall, the study provides insights into the demographic and spatiotemporal characteristics of patients managed with PFNA-2. The findings suggest that IT fracture is more common among males and older individuals. The spatiotemporal parameters can help in understanding the gait patterns and functional abilities of patients managed with PFNA-2, which could inform the development of rehabilitation and postoperative care strategies. However, the small sample size and lack of a control group limit the generalizability of the study's findings.

Author's contribution

Both the authors and the co-authors were responsible for developing and conducting the data collection, musculoskeletal modelling, and analyses of the results. Additionally, Arjun Sivakumar took the lead in writing the manuscript. All authors contributed to shaping the research, analysis, and manuscript and provided feedback to improve the quality of the study.

References

1. Macheras, G.A., Koutsostathis, S.D., Galanakis, S., Kateros, K. and Papadakis, S.A., 2012. Does PFNA II avoid lateral cortex impingement for unstable peritrochanteric fractures? *Clinical Orthopaedics and Related Research*, 470, pp.3067-3076.
2. Chang, Shi-Min, et al. "Mismatch of the short straight cephalomedullary nail (PFNA-2) with the anterior bow of the femur in an Asian population." *Journal of orthopaedic trauma* 28.1 (2014): 17-22.
3. Sambandam, Senthil Nathan, Jayadev Chandrasekharan, Varatharaj Mounasamy, and Cyril Mauffrey. "Intertrochanteric fractures: a review of fixation methods." *European Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery & Traumatology* 26 (2016): 339-353.
4. Bhaskarwar S, Jagani GC, Viegas AG, Panse JB, Desai A, Kale V. A prospective study to evaluate the clinical and functional outcomes in the management of unstable extracapsular proximal femoral fractures using proximal femoral nail with a helical blade construct (PFNA-2) at a tertiary care hospital. *International Journal of Orthopaedics*. 2022; 8(1):648-53.
5. Jarnlo GB, Thorngren KG, Background factors to hip fractures. *Clinorthop* 1993; 287:41-49
6. Schumpelick W, Jantzen PM. A new principle in the operative treatment of trochanteric frac-

- ture of the hip, *J. Bone Joint Surg* 1988; 70-A: v 1297-303.
7. Tosounidis TH, Castillo R, Kanakaris NK, Giannoudis PV. Common complications in hip fracture surgery: Tips/tricks and solutions to avoid them. *Injury*. 2015 Nov 1; 46:S3-11.
 8. Kazemian GH, Manafi AR, Najafi F, Najafi MA. Treatment of intertrochanteric fractures in elderly highrisk patients: dynamic hip screw vs. external fixation. *Injury*. 2014 Mar 1; 45(3):568-72.
 9. Chaitanya M, Mittal A, Rallapalli R, Biju R, Prasad YS. Comparison of Dynamic Hip Screw and Plate with Proximal Femoral Nail in Trochanteric Fractures of Femur. *IOSR J Dent Med Sci* 2015; 14(4):73-82.
 10. Simmermacher RKJ, Bosch AM, Van der Werken C. The AO/ASIF- Proximal femoral nail: a new device for the treatment of unstable proximal femoral fractures. *Injury* 1999; 30: 327-32.
 11. Albaker, A. B. (2021). Proximal femoral nail anti-rotation-2 in intertrochanteric fractures: Experience from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Advances in Human Biology*, 11(Suppl 1), S116-S119.
 12. Swaroop S, Gupta P, Bawari R, Marya SK, Patnaik S. Factors affecting the outcome of unstable intertrochanteric fractures managed with proximal femoral nail anti-rotation 2: A prospective outcome study in elderly Indian population. *Cureus*. 2020 Dec 8; 12(12).
 13. Pan, S., Liu, X. H., Feng, T., Kang, H. J., Tian, Z. G., & Lou, C. G. (2017). Influence of different great trochanteric entry points on the outcome of intertrochanteric fractures: a retrospective cohort study. *BMC musculoskeletal disorders*, 18, 1-9.
 14. Mallya S, Kamath SU, Madegowda A, Krishnamurthy SL, Jain MK, Holla R. Comparison of radiological and functional outcome of unstable intertrochanteric femur fractures treated using PFN and PFNA-2 in patients with osteoporosis. *European Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery & Traumatology*. 2019 Jul 1; 29:1035-42.
 15. Öner, K., Durusoy, S. and Özer, A., 2020. A new proximal femoral nail antirotation design: Is it effective in preventing varus collapse and cut-out?. *Joint diseases and related surgery*, 31(3), p.426.
 16. Mandal DM, Kumar R, Kumar D, Singh D, Sagar V, Kumar N, Chaudhary R. Comparative study of PFN vs PFNA 2 in intertrochanteric fractures: A randomised control trial. *International Journal of Orthopaedics*. 2020; 6(4):461-5.
 17. Gordon KE, Ferris DP, Kuo AD. Metabolic and mechanical energy costs of reducing vertical center of mass movement during gait. *Archives of physical medicine and rehabilitation*. 2009 Jan 1; 90(1):136-44.
 18. Verhulp E, van Rietbergen B, Huiskes R. Load distribution in the healthy and osteoporotic human proximal femur during a fall to the side. *Bone*. 2008 Jan 1; 42(1):30-5.